

Original Article

Death and Dasein: A Heideggerian Study of Jean Paul Sartre's *The Wall*

Malik Hassan Raza¹ & Dr. Tauqeer Ahmad Lak

¹ University of Gujrat

² Department of Sociology & Criminology, University of Sargodha, Pakistan <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8230-7679>

Abstract

The present study aims at describing the death as a mirror for one's existential search for meaning in one's experiences. It does not focus on death as a singular event. It, rather, describes the fragility of human existence. The moral effect of fragility of human existence is that it ascribes value to the limited time available. Heidegger's existentialist perspective has been used as a theoretical lens for the faithful description of death experience of Pablo. He is a war-captive who has been awarded death sentence. His project of authenticity starts while he takes his death as a possibility. His intuitive judgment yields significant facts about the fragility of existence. Existentialists do not view mortality as merely an opposite of life. They claim that it has a constitutive role to play in the appropriation of the Dasein to make the realization of being-in-the-world possible. A Dasein can only be authentic if it is aware of its finite temporality. This holding onto the truth of death leads to the primordial certainty of Dasein's being-in-the-world. Pablo's understanding of death as a Dasein's *ownmost* possibility helps him reconstitute his philosophies of life afterwards. Heidegger's concept of death as a possibility of impossibility plays a significant role in Pablo's perception of death through a subjective experience.

Keywords: Death Experience, Heidegger's existentialist perspective, Jean Paul Sartre's *The Wall*

Introduction

Jean Paul Sartre is a French philosopher and writer. His literary works are a manifestation of his philosophical views. However, his view regarding the possibility of death in his short story *The Wall* requires another perspective to fully describe the different phenomenological senses of death. Heidegger's existentialist meaning of death provides that framework which discusses death as a possibility constitutive of the appropriation of the Dasein. *The Wall* is one of the greatest existentialist works. The background of the story is the Spanish civil war which began on July 18, 1936. The title of the story suggests the inescapability of death. It is also the symbol of inevitability and unknowing of one's death as the firing squad positions the prisoners against the wall. Three war captives including Pablo Ibbieta are sentenced to death. They spend the whole night musing over the experience of death. Pablo is promised that if he shares the location of Ramon Gris, they will release him. Pablo takes his death as a possibility unlike other two prisoners who take it as an actuality. He plays a trick at the time of his execution. He shares the wrong location of comrade Ramon Gris. Unfortunately, Gris moves to the location shared by Pablo. They shoot him and Pablo is temporarily spared.

The project of the authenticity of the Dasein aims at affirming the bitter truths of human conditions. Sartre and Heidegger share some common grounds in this project. They agree that affirming the finitude is a prompt to authentic action. Sartre, however, disagrees with Heidegger's formulation of concept of death as

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the own most possibility of Dasein. He claims that it is not among Dasein's possibilities at all. For him, death is non-experiencable and hence cannot be anticipated. However, Heidegger (2001) states that the death is the ownmost possibility of Dasein. He claims that the potential of the Dasein lies in bridging the possibility of death (in present) with the inevitability of death (in future). So, the present is always haunted by this possibility arising from its own finitude. It is imperative for the Dasein to acknowledge both the finitude and inevitability of death. A person must understand his own death than experiencing the deaths of others in general. Heidegger (2001) says that "The non-relational character of death, as understood in anticipation, individualises Dasein down to itself" (p. 308). This non-relational character of death makes a person authentic and genuine than a replica or a copy. Pablo's phenomenological struggle to understand the existentialist meaning of death and its constitutive role in the appropriation of Dasein can best be described through Heidegger's idea of possibility of death.

Literature Review:

Twentieth century has witnessed traumatic incidents of suppression through dictatorial power and ultra-nationalism. The Falangist party in Spain mass murdered everyone who opposed or was suspected of opposition. Jean Paul Sartre juxtaposes this idea by presenting the reader with three war captives in death row being observed and studied by a doctor. The doctor has been appointed to record their psychological responses in the last hours of their lives. Pablo Ibeita takes doctor as the only person who is alive in the room as he can think about tomorrow. The other three are walking dead for Pablo. However, as the story proceeds on, Pablo learns that the doctor is no longer alive than them. Although he has decades to live yet, his existence is less authentic than that of other men in the room. Sartre (1939) narrates that Ibeita's understanding of death reveals that "several hours or several years of waiting is all the same when you have lost the illusion of being eternal" (p. 109). It, further, leads him to conclude that he has "lost the illusion of being eternal" (p. 109). The understanding of death introduces the subject with reality that he has only a limited time to live. Sartre has chosen these three characters to refer to trinity consisting of protection, guidance and help from divinity.

Death has been a subject of great debate since primordial times. Greco-Roman scholarship has been potentially contributing in it since the time of Homer and his contemporaries. Church and Anderson (1951) quote Socrates in *Phaedo* 64a as, "I am afraid that other people do not realize that the one aim of those who practice philosophy in the proper manner is to practice for dying and death" (p. 8). Those philosophers who believe in the afterlife conceptions view death as a gateway to transcendental existence. They don't approach it as a structural limit to life. Lucretius, on the contrary, says that death is simply non-existence. According to him, only the death is immortal. Further, he says that the best way to approach death is not to approach it at all. Epicurus expresses similar thoughts by saying that our thought should not concern us. Similarly, Seneca's *The Consolationes* lends an advice on approaching death (Kassel 28). He makes distinction between Subjective experience of one's own death and that of others. The fragility of human existence is moralizing for him. The best ethical response to death is to master the fear of death. He, once, wished somebody could come back from the dead and tell us what to expect. Homer's *Odyssey* is one such account of death in which Odysseus visits the dead and comes back to relate his experiences. Death has always been a favorite subject for ancient classics. It came to surface in the Renaissance age with the rebirth of classical antiquity. The writers, however, only imitated the outer trappings of classical ideas. Their main focus was on scientific interpretations of death but it did not lend itself easily to scientific analysis. Eventually, these themes disappeared in the post-Renaissance period. Spinoza was convinced that the modern man should focus on the life more than death. Friedrich Nietzsche said that the thoughts about life were more valuable than the thoughts about death.

Death re-emerged as a philosophical problem in the twentieth century. Freud (1901) claimed that we did not believe in our own death. He said that every one of us, unconsciously, believed in his own immortality. A radical shift occurred in the approaches to study death after the introduction of phenomenology by Edmund Husserl. Husserl's reflections on embodiment and intersubjectivity provided conceptual tools for the study of phenomenon of death. However, his epistemic concerns of presuppositionless philosophy could not find favor among his contemporaries.

Heidegger (2001) proposed that understanding was always ahead of itself. Moreover, a 'forestructure' of assumptions and beliefs was inherent in understanding which guided interpretation. Heidegger's concept

of anticipatory structure of understanding dragged Husserl's concern with epistemology into ontology. However, his model departed from the cautious avoidance of speculation. Merleau-Ponty expanded Heideggerian ideas into his existential phenomenology. Soren Kierkegaard (1849), in *Sickness unto Death*, warned against the study of death as an event happening in the intersubjective time. Further, in *Concluding Unscientific Postscript*, he said that if death were to come tomorrow, the subject would think whether he was starting something that was worth starting. Such uncertainty, according to him, may lead to confusion and indecision. Kierkegaard and Lowrie (1941) narrate "my dying is by no means something in general; for others, my dying is some such thing in general" (p. 309). The death is not given to all involved in a similar way. Although the dying subject, the bereaved and a casual passer-by live in the same-space-time, yet they should not take it as a singular event that is progressing in time foregoing other events. Phenomenology provided existentialists with a philosophical attitude which could view human life from inside. Together, phenomenology and Existentialism, became faithful companions to each other focusing on the facts about individual self. They revisited the metaphysics and epistemological claims about death. Martin Heidegger's phenomenological insights of death present it as a certainty of being-in-the-world. Wild (1962) describes Heidegger's formulation of the concept of death as "packed with suggestive interpretations" (p. 308). Similarly, Demske (2014) has appreciated time and again the originality of Heidegger's conception. He says that Heidegger has conferred upon theoretical formulation of death "a new ontological depth" (p. 2). Barrett (1964), in the same way, proclaims that Heidegger's analysis has offered an insightful interpretation "in his whole picture of man" (p. 62).

Heidegger's formulation of death as 'possibility' is presented in opposition to 'actuality'. The problem with the understanding of death is that most of the people take it as an actuality. This attitude towards death weakens its possibility. Heidegger describes it as our uttermost, and our unoutsrippable possibility. Dasein, according to Heidegger (2001), "determines its own character as the kind of entity it is, and it does so in every case in terms of a possibility which it itself is and which it understands" (Pp. 303-304). So, this 'possibility' does not refer to an empty logical possibility or contingency of something present-at-hand. Heidegger's concept of 'possibility' is complex and requires illustrations. Demske (1970) supports his argument by saying that Heidegger's formulation of 'possibility' "refers to the open future for which the Dasein can decide" (p. 62). Thus, it indicates what Dasein "can be, do or become" (p 62). Macquarrie (1968), in his book *Martin Heidegger*, seconds this idea.

Derrida (1993) contradicts with Heidegger in terms of weight indicating that it is the impossibility of appropriation. He reverses Heideggerian appropriation as the inappropriable in appropriation. He calls it exappropriation. Thus, for Derrida (1993), the most proper sense of appropriation is the condition of remaining inappropriable. He quotes Jean Luc Nancy's concept of weight residing at the center of the thought and inspite of thought. This shows that existence weighs on thought from the outside. Derrida (1993) discusses existential meaning of death in *Aporias*. He claims that Heidegger approaches death as a 'possibility' and not 'impossibility'. He further explains it as the possibility of a being-able-not-to or of a no-longer-being-able-to. He says Heidegger has not referred to it as the impossibility of a being-able-to.

Derrida (1993) remodels Heidegger's appropriation of the inappropriable on expropriation of the proper which he refers to as exappropriation. According to him, the most proper sense of existence is on the condition of remaining inappropriable. He reverses "the possibility of impossible" into "the impossibility of possible". The term "possibility of impossible" is used in the Heidegger's *Being and Time* referring to the existential meaning of death. Derrida (1993) discusses it in *Aporias* claiming Heidegger's conception of death as a possibility and not impossibility. For him, death is a possibility for Dasein. However, he refers to the expression "the possibility of impossible" as aporetic.

Derrida's stance is that Heidegger has approached possibility as impossibility whereas heideggerian appropriation is possibility of impossibility. The aporetic moment which has been pointed out by Derrida is the responsibility of the Dasein arising from its own impossibility. Derrida (1993) thinks that Heidegger has referred to appropriation in his thinking. However, Heidegger situates expropriation at the heart of responsibility. For instance, if we take a look at the concept of Dasein, it means 'exists as thrown' as it is 'brought into its there not of its own accord'. Therefore, a Dasein can never appropriate its origin by getting

back behind its coming into being. This view presents existence as being called to appropriate one's own being from the ground up. So, the self which is struggling to lay the ground of itself can never gain power over it. According to Heidegger (2001), this is the very impossibility that Dasein must make its own and possibilize. In other words, this is the very inappropriable that Dasein must appropriate. Responsibility can therefore be described as the paradoxical appropriation of an inappropriable. Heidegger speaks of responsibility in terms of carrying weight. The burdensome character of Dasein is actually the characteristic of being of factual life which is hard to bear. So, that weight is the weight of existence itself. Heidegger claims that this weight is charged with the responsibility of the Dasein appropriated by it.

Sartre (1956) presents death as a brute fact. It is a worn-out battle between I and the Other. Ontologically speaking, death is not a structure of the for-itself. He states, "to be dead is to be a prey for the living" (p. 543). For Sartre, death is not an essential source of meaning of life. Similarly, the dying subject owes to other his meaning. The facticity of death is a restriction on one's freedom. Death steals from us the opportunity to create meaning in life. Once dead, we fail to have a perspective. We become being-for-others when we die. We are judged by the perspectives of others. We are known by their individual experience. Our freedom in a situation has no power over death. Sartre (1956) puts it as "my death is not fixed by me; the sequence of the universe determines it" (p. 564). According to Schumacher (2010), Sartre (1956) proposes a different model of ontology and contradicts with Heidegger's concept of Being-towards-death calling it a "sleight of hand." (p. 91)

The Wall describes Sartre's existentialist view of death. For him, death is only a brute fact. It does not provide us an opportunity to produce meaning in life. However, Heidegger describes it as a possibility of impossibility. Dasein accepts death as his ownmost and possibilizes it is re-contextualizing his existence. Pablo's understanding of his death helps him re-examine his commitment with Concha and Roman Gris.

Theoretical Framework:

Phenomenology is the study of the structures of experience. It was founded in the 20th century by a German philosopher Edmund Husserl. He introduced it as a presuppositionless philosophy. Phenomenological struggle starts with suspending the existing views and knowledge about the phenomenon. Jacques Derrida criticized the theories of presupposition lessness and intentionality. He claimed that the non-presence and otherness was internal to the presence. Hence, the knowledge is perspectival and limited. Husserlian Phenomenology contrives the originary givenness and ideality of the living present. However, it ignores the empirical impurity in its ideality which results from the ever eminent intrusion from outside. This intrusion, further, challenges the originary givenness of living present. Husserl tries to exclude outside through the means of transcendental reduction. Husserlian Phenomenology functions on the basis of reductionist approach. Derrida and Ponty criticize this aspect of phenomenology. They claim that it cannot escape what is constitutive of itself. Similarly, it cannot purify what is essentially impure. Derrida (1973), for instance, in his work *Voice and Phenomenon: Introduction to the Problem of the Sign in Husserl's Phenomenology*, quotes that phenomenology is tormented from outside. This answers the husserlian claim of purifying what is essentially impure. Similarly, Merleau-Ponty and Smith (2015) in the *Phenomenology of Perception* state that the phenomenological reduction can never be completed. These two positions challenging the reductionist approach from inside and outside both, however, are not the same. Derrida insists on the inappropriable alterity whereas Ponty theorizes the conception of alterity. Derrida's deconstructive analysis of no-presence or alterity challenges the purity of extra-mundane monadological sphere. It is modelled on the western metaphysics which bestows an exorbitant privilege upon presence to the detriment of non-presence. Through this model, he explores purity of expression and mundanity. This rigorous distinction between purity of expression and mundanity thrusts western philosophy into metaphysics of presence. This suggests the expression of the pure ideality is only repetition of the same expression and it cannot express itself with the contingent variation of mundanity.

Heidegger's theoretical formulations illustrate departure from Husserl's phenomenological ideas. Heidegger's approach to investigate the meaning of Being in the existing world focuses on the intersubjective ontological perspective. He interprets existence over the time. Being and Time is in a way a critique of Husserl's transcendental phenomenology. Crowell (2005) calls it "a dynamic of attraction and repulsion" (p.

49). He criticizes Husserl's principle of intentionality. He is concerned with pre-theoretical conditions which generate intentionality. He reformulated Husserl's formal ontology into fundamental ontology making the transcendental consciousness as Dasein. Similarly, Husserlian intentionality was changed into Being-in-the-world (pre-intentional openness to world). Dasein exists as a thrown projection plus falling. This projective aspect creates anticipatory structure making Dasein as a Being-ahead-of-itself landing in the realm of possibilities as incomplete. Death is complementary to Dasein's existence. One may argue that Dasein appropriates his own death through the death of others. However, Heidegger (2001) says, "The dying of Others is not something which we experience in a genuine sense; at most we are always just 'there alongside'" (p. 282). He claims that Dasein cannot understand its death as actual but it can relate it as a possibility. This is because when death becomes actual, the Dasein is no longer. Death is thus "a possibility of impossibility". It is an omnipresent possibility which cannot become actual. Heidegger calls it the 'ownmost' as the relations to others disappear. This non-relationality makes it a "possibility which is one's ownmost" (p. 294). So, when we take the possibility of our not-Being, our own Being-able-to is comprehensible. This leads to

Analysis:

The Wall (1939) is Juan Paul Sartre's magnum opus. It describes the death experiences of three war-captives, Pablo, Juan and Tom, who have been condemned with death sentence. They start shivering with the cold after receiving death warrant. They start pondering over the phenomenon of death. This lends them an opportunity to be exposed to the authentic self. The project of authenticity as described by the Heidegger requires Dasein to embrace the bitter truths of human conditions. Tom narrates different accounts of the implementation of death sentence. Juan is greatly terrified to hear these accounts. Tom tries to sympathize with him but in vain. Pablo realizes that Tom is trying to delay his death by sympathizing with Juan. He feels that Juan has changed and he will never be young again. Pablo is the protagonist of the story. His struggle to find the meaning of death starts through bereavement. He is clinically observing the behavior of Juan and Tom. He feels that they have turned grey out of the fear of death. They are approached by a Belgian doctor who is taking stock of their behavior. Pablo feels that the doctor is unaffected by the death. He is cold and hungry because he can look forward to tomorrow. Tom tells Pablo that he has killed seven people since August but he has never tried to understand his own death. Dasein can never appropriate his own death through the death of others. Heidegger (2001) says that "The dying of Others is not something which we experience in a genuine sense; at most we are always just 'there alongside'" (p. 282). Dasein cannot experience death as actual. He can only relate it as a possibility. This is a kind of omnipresent possibility that cannot become actual.

They soon realize that the experience of death through bereavement is not going to answer their quest for the existential meaning of death. Tom is annoyed at having failed to understand it. He says, "It's like a nightmare, "You want to think something, you always have the impression that it's all right, that you're going to understand and then it slips, it escapes you and fades away" (p. 8). Tom is distracted by his anxiety which he has developed to counter the violent nature of event. He is unable to understand death as an end point. Heidegger says that the Dasein is no longer when the death becomes natural. So, this is not possible for Dasein to enact his own death as an end point. Tom is disturbed by this thought as he says "I see my corpse; that's not hard but I'm the one who sees it, with my eyes" (p. 8). He is disturbed by this thought. Heidegger's idea of anticipatory structure of consciousness explains it. He says that we are always ahead of our understanding of something. Similarly, Heidegger claims that the death creates opportunity for the Dasein to be an authentic self. The understanding of death fills Dasein with anxiousness. This anxiousness, he says, is different from fear. We are always afraid of a direct object such as a snake. Anxiousness is linked with the futility of existence and nothingness in life. This is why when Tom tries to touch the bench, he shudders not out of fear but anxiety. Pablo says that, "It was his death which Tom had just touched on the bench" (p. 12). He says that he would not amuse himself with the idea of touching the bench. Sartre (1956) disagrees with Heidegger saying that the possibility of death does not affect authenticity in a dramatic way as the freedom does. He takes death as another part of life. It happens when it happens or if Dasein can choose it to happen. He says "I can neither discover my death nor wait for it nor adopt an attitude towards it" (p. 697). Pablo has seen people dying in the war but the experience of his own death has affected him differently. He feels that something is going to happen to him which he cannot understand yet. He says "I told myself "Now it starts"" (p. 5). He has lost

control over his body. He describes it as “I wasn’t exactly cold, but I couldn’t feel my arms and shoulders anymore” (p. 3). The terror is sweeping through his body. He says that his body is not his own anymore. He says that he feels crushed “under an enormous weight” (p. 5). He tells that he had been “dripping for an hour and had not felt it” (p. 6). He decides to understand the existential meaning of death instead of delaying it through bereavement. He is desperately trying to understand his death as he says that he did not want to die “like an animal, he wanted to understand it” (p. 11). Similarly, at another place, he says, “I want to die cleanly” (p. 13). In order to act out of anxiousness, he plays a trick to delay his death. He shares a false location of Roman Gris which turns out to be true accidentally. He is temporarily saved. Pablo is different in his approach to understand death unlike Juan and Tom who try to get it as actual. For Pablo, it is a possibility of impossibility which gives him courage to take control of his death and postpone it. His understanding of death as a possibility plays a constitutive role in his philosophy towards life. He says that he has changed altogether. He is more genuine and authentic now. Nothing is more important to him than his own life. He says that he admires Roman Gris but he is not going to die at his place. Similarly, his girlfriend Concha, he says, will be grieved to receive the news of his death but she will, after some time, attend to other trivial things in her life. He knows that nobody will die his death. He is no longer leading his life in the bad faith. He says “My friendship for him had died a little while before dawn at the same time as my love for Concha, at the same time as my desire to live. Undoubtedly I thought highly of him: he was tough. But it was not for this reason that I consented to die in his place; his life had no more value than mine” (Pp. 15-16). Pablo embraced his authentic self through the finitude of his mortality. At this moment, nothing was more important or valuable to him than his own life.

Conclusion:

The study offers useful insights into the understanding of the phenomenon of death as it presents itself in the consciousness of three war captives. It is described as a very unique human experience. Prior to the emergence of Greek thought, the concept of death was not rationally systematized. It largely depended on epistemologically pessimistic premise which stated death clutched in the hands of a mysterious other. Greeks presented it as a knowable and meaningful experience in the rationally ordered universe. However, Significance of death was only cosmic prior to the existentialist quest for the meaning of death. It did not have any individual significance. It presented a depersonalized view of death. Heideggerian discourse of being-towards-death holds an important position in the discourse on phenomenological project of authentic self. The concept of death as a singular event is re-contextualized to describe the fragility of human existence. The Dasein takes death as his ownmost responsibility and possibilizes it. A faithful description of Pablo’s experience of death reveals the possibility of realization of being-in-the-world. It shows that death is not an opposite of life. It, rather, has a constitutive role to play in the appropriation of Dasein towards its authentic self. This view of death presents it as a mirror focusing on one’s existential search for meaning in one’s experiences

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